

THE ROLE OF LITERATURE IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article talks about the importance of using fiction in teaching Russian. It is emphasized that it is the work with fiction that contributes to the familiarization with the national and cultural specifics of speech behavior in the country of the language being studied; helps to form students' understanding of various spheres of modern life of another society, its history and culture.

Currently, the main approach to teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities is professionally oriented education. The main task is to develop various types of competencies - reading, writing, speaking. According to the majority of specialists, methodologists in the field of teaching foreign languages in non-linguistic universities, a foreign language from the first days of study at a university is a necessary means of forming the professional consciousness of a non-linguistic specialist [4]. The ultimate goal of education, therefore, is the formation in students of the foundations of a professionally oriented secondary linguistic personality, the content of which is determined by the peculiarities of the spheres and situations of professional intercultural communication [2].

In this regard, the problem of choosing educational material is extremely relevant. Textual material still remains one of the main sources for the development of foreign language competencies. Work with the text is aimed both at summarizing and extracting the necessary information from the text, and at the formation of oral communication competencies in the studied foreign language. Recently, preference has been given to authentic texts in the studied foreign language, corresponding to the direction of students' education.

At the same time, works of art that are directly related to the professional interests of future specialists remain unreasonably forgotten. They allow not only to form the skills of professional communication, but also to create preconditions for the development of intercultural communication [1].

Recently, several works have appeared on the use of literary texts in teaching foreign languages to students of non-linguistic specialties [2]. This article will focus on teaching Russian to students of non-linguistic universities and the possibility of using literary texts in this process. Undoubtedly, in this case, training should be conducted on professionally oriented tests. But it should be borne in mind that in fiction you can find works related to a

certain professional field. The peculiarity of teaching students in the field of medicine is that the focus is on the person, and, consequently, professional communication will be communication about the person. Therefore, the use of literary texts seems quite relevant and useful.

In recent years, the role of fiction in curricula as a main component and source of authentic texts in Russian has again attracted attention. The use of fiction in the process of teaching a foreign language is experiencing a renaissance for a number of reasons. Part of the traditional approaches to teaching a foreign language using literary materials, where the learning process focused on the functional use of the language being studied, has become less popular. However, in various methods of teaching a foreign language, the role of literary texts is now overestimated, and many teachers have begun to consider literary texts as providing a wide range of linguistic and cultural information, as an effective incentive for students to develop the ability to express their thoughts in other languages, and also as a potential source of student motivation.

The choice of literary material today is no longer limited to canonical texts from literary sources in countries such as the United Kingdom and the United States, but includes the work of writers from different countries and cultures using various forms of the Russian language. It is well known that the content of teaching foreign languages should be aimed at introducing students not only to a new way of verbal communication, but also to the culture of the people who speak the target language, to the national and cultural specifics of speech behavior in the country of the target language. language through the culture of the peoples inhabiting the country of the language being studied (more precisely, through the dialogue of their national culture and culture). It helps to form students' understanding of various areas of modern life of another society, its history and culture [3] teaching another people) must be carried out constantly, starting from the first steps of studying the subject. Introducing foreign language learners to the literature of another nation undoubtedly helps to develop an understanding of other cultures, introduces them to their features and differences, and fosters a tolerant attitude towards representatives of other communities. At the same time, excerpts from literary works often discuss universal themes, such as love, war, and loss, which are not always covered by the main content of textbooks.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language is the formation of communicative competence as the ability and willingness to communicate in a foreign language. Achieving this goal, i.e., the implementation of communicative activity, is possible when mastering a certain content of training, one of the components of which are skills and abilities.

Literary texts are a rich source of linguistic information for practical assignments, and can help students develop all the basic skills - speaking, listening, reading and writing - as an ideal complement to illustrating the use of grammatical structures and the use of new vocabulary [5]. Modern students come across literature that differs both in time and periods of what is described, and in styles and genres, get acquainted with different aspects of human experience (for example, philosophical, ethical, aesthetic). Among these texts are fiction and popular science, classical and contemporary works. The artistic language of literary works contributes to the emergence of emotions in readers, and awakens the cognitive abilities of students, immersing them in the content of the text.

The READING section in most foreign and domestic educational and methodological

complexes offers a wide range of texts of general interest; contributing to the acquisition of new information and understanding of the needs of society; understanding the culture of their country and the countries of the language being studied.

When choosing literary texts independently, an Russian teacher should take into account the needs, motivation, interests, cultural background and language level of students. However, one of the main factors to consider is whether the proposed work can arouse student interest and generate strong, positive reactions. An interesting text will be one that contains new problematic information, opens a "window" into the world of a different culture, affects its feelings and emotions, etc. [3]. Informative and interesting texts are likely to have a positive impact on the development of skills to analyze linguistic and extralinguistic features. Also, of great importance is the choice of books related to the real experiences and emotions of students. Speaking of language complexity, it is quite obvious that if the language of a literary work is simple, this may make it easier to understand the literary text, but for a trained reader, the "complexity" of the language will not be an obstacle to reading. There are several approaches to the study of literary material. The works of classical and modern writers can be studied in their original form, in the original, as well as in a simplified or abridged version, the so-called Easy Reading. For learners of Russian and other foreign languages, more and more works of fiction are being published, written specifically for this category of readers.

The types of literary texts that can be used for both classroom and out-of-class reading include:

short stories

novels

fairy tales

plays

song lyrics

Although the world of novels, plays, or short stories is imaginary, it provides a full and colorful setting in which characters from many social or regional groups can be described. Texts can be supplemented with audio texts, music CDs, movie clips, podcasts, which will positively affect the sensory perception of the material [4]. Reading literary texts is inextricably linked with written speech, which can serve as a motivating source. The use of a written language gives students the opportunity to focus more deeply on linguistic and stylistic features (literacy, expressiveness, etc.), allows them to develop critical thinking skills, the ability to analyze, independence, which will inevitably contribute to the development of general academic literacy [5].

Thus, learning to read fiction in Russian will open to students a rich source of authentic material for the development of literary competence, for better assimilation and enrichment of the passive vocabulary; will develop knowledge about the culture of the language being studied and, in general, will contribute to the main goal of learning.

All the works included in the manual describe the features of life, culture and relationships between people in their professional environment. Accordingly, both the vocabulary and the style of communication and grammar will correspond to the conditions in which the narration or conversation is being conducted. At the same time, special attention should be paid to professional communication, since the conversations of heroes or just people among themselves in the stories allow us to draw the necessary conclusions about the difference in professional and everyday communication, the use of special and general colloquial designations of the same phenomena, which is very typical for the Russian language. It is well known that in Russian there are words (terms) borrowed from the Latin language, and native Russian words denoting the same concept. And if in professional communication, as a rule, the former is used, then in everyday life the latter prevail, which should be especially emphasized when working with literary texts. This is one of the differences between professional and everyday communication, which students need to pay attention to. Given all of the above, it should be noted that an important role in the process of teaching a foreign language is played by the professionalism of the teacher. Carrying out the professionalization of education, a teacher of a foreign language - Russian, must also have subject competence sufficient to discuss certain professional issues in a foreign language, to assess the suitability of the selected materials for the educational process in a foreign language and their significance for a particular discipline.

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